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Theory and Practice of Documentation Science as an integrated course in training students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies

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The contemporary society needs specialists who can deal with organizing work with documents in all subsystems of social communications. Such specialists are trained within the specialty “Information, Library and Archival Studies”. In this context, the contents of compulsory courses are of great importance, in particular, the course “Theory and practice of documentation science” as an integrated course in training students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies.

The compulsory course “Theory and practice of documentation science” was implemented into the bachelor’s degree program in Information, Library and Archival Studies in the 2021-2022 study year as a result of combining separate courses “Documentation Science” and “Office Work”. It was initiated by taking into account the necessity of updating an education program according to the modern society’s needs for training qualified specialists in Information, Library and Archival Studies. Besides, in many universities, there is still a tendency of teaching the above-mentioned courses separately, even at different courses, which is not logical.

Documentation Science is defined as knowledge about documents and activities connected with them, so-called document and communication activities. Therefore, it was a logical merging of theory and practice of two disciplines, which are based on knowledge, and practice of working with documents. It is considered to be an integrated compulsory course that is geared toward forming systems of theoretical and applied knowledge about documents as components of social communication, their essences, structures, functions, classifications, as well as their main types and patterns functioning in the process of organizing modern office work and document management. This course is taught for freshmen during two semesters. In the first semester, students get theoretical knowledge about various documents and their specifics and in the second one – applied knowledge about using documents in professional fields of their activity, in particular, in-office work. The course is very important for freshmen, as they could understand the essence of their specialty concerning the organization of working with documents.

The course “Theory and Practice of Documentation Science” consists of 4 modules including the following subjects:

- 1) the theoretical foundations of documentation science as generalizing science of the document;
- 2) specifics of certain types of documents in documentation science;
- 3) office work as a practical documentation science in management activities;

4) documentation of management activities.

This course is practice-oriented as it allows mastering students' document work skills. For example, when studying advertising documents students make their own video, graphic, and multimedia advertisements for teacher's tasks. Diversities of documents are investigated in special document centers such as libraries, museums, archives, etc. Classes are taken by students at such centers to get knowledge about organizing work with documents there, in the real environment. Students also get knowledge about current law documents concerning regimentation of functioning office documents. When studying office work students get practical skills in making different types of management documentation such as organizational and administrative, reference and information, personnel and contract ones, as well as business correspondence in traditional and electronic variants. Students are taught to make templates for documents not only in Word but also in merging documents in Word and Excel, which is of great importance when making a lot of similar types of documents with different data.

Taking into account society's needs in using electronic document management systems, students get practical skills of working with some of them during either traditional or online classes, in particular, Ascod, to be more exact its version called Ascod online.

Among the pros of studying Ascod online as a document management system by students are the following ones:

- it combines internal and external electronic document management systems; has a simple interface;
- high speed of documents receipt and transfer;
- service availability 24/7 from any device;
- ability to use an electronic signature;
- protected carrier and Mobile ID, no additional software required.

It is very important for students to have practical skills with contemporary document management systems as in the conditions of the pandemic and war all organizations are used to working with them. Therefore, employers are interested in hiring specialists who know the main principles and techniques of working with such systems.

After mastering the compulsory course, students majoring in Information, Library and Archival Studies will get the following outcomes, which are components of their qualified training including the following ones:

- managing documentation processes of institutions, using electronic means of document management, organizing reference and office activities;
- summarizing, analyzing, and synthesizing information about activities related to its search, accumulation, storage and use in modern organizations, institutions and enterprises;

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- knowing, understanding and applying in practice, legislative and sectoral regulations on implementation of information activities;
- ensuring efficient functioning of document and communication systems;
- carrying out a search for information in various sources to solve professional problems on the provision of information services and products relevant to inquiries consumers;
- deepening the acquired and gaining new professional knowledge to ensure competitiveness in the labor market of the modern socio-cultural environment.

Thus, taking into account the above-mentioned, it is possible to state that the implementation into bachelor curricula of such an integrated course as “Theory and Practice of Documentation Science” will promote the training of highly-qualified specialists in the field of Information, Library and Archival Studies thanks to its practice-oriented content which is geared toward meeting labor market’s modern requirements.